

Research on the Application of Psychological Healing through Art

Xiangkun ZHU

ABSTRACT

With the development of society, Maslow's demand on people began to pay more and more attention to their spirit in the field of a situation and start to reflect more on their happy or unhappy happiness, as well as their psychological status is how it influences their behavior and even the enterprise performance and the condition of a happy family. Along with this trend, more and more different ways of psychological healing are coming into view. Art therapy is a very cross-boundary approach because it not only exists in the traditional field of psychology but also combines art, a different discipline. What impact will this cross-boundary collaboration bring to psychological therapy? And what kind of practical significance and achievements will such a cross-disciplinary collision bring to some application fields? This paper shows us the background, purpose, and various forms of art healing. We summarize the effects of art healing and its impact on clients in various situations. Art therapy has a very healthy and positive effect on different types of customers, whether in mental illness or mental sub-health or does not have psychological symptoms. Moreover, art therapy can be applied in various industries, making everyone's life. It can make every business organization and society happier and more efficient, bringing a diversified positive impact.

***Keywords* : Art therapy, art, psychotherapy, organizational mental health competence, coaching, counseling**

Chapter 1 Introduction	1156
1.1 Research Background	1156
1.2 Research purpose and significance	1157
Chapter 2 The Link Between Art and Art Therapy	1159
2.1 Definition of art	1159
2.2 Psychological healing and mental sub-health	1160
2.2.1 Psychological healing	1160
2.2.2 Mental sub-health	1161
2.3 How to improve the effectiveness of psychological healing through art	1162
Chapter 3 Current Application and Analysis of Art Therapy	1163
3.1 Types of Art Therapy	1163
3.2 Application Status and Effect of Art Therapy	1164
3.3 Quantitative and qualitative analysis of art therapy user feedback	1172
Chapter Four Application Prospects of Art Therapy	1176
4.1 Application in adult corporate training and adult coaching	1176
4.2 Use in adolescents	1177
4.3 Application in entertainment life	1179
Chapter Five Current Difficulties and Challenges	1181
5.1 Market Demand	1181
5.2 The Ability of Art Therapy Coaches	1181
5.3 Willingness to pay	1181
Chapter 6 Conclusion	1182
References	1183

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

A. Research Background

In today's society, Maslow's needs move up. People began to pay more attention to individualistic questions, such as: Who am I? What is the purpose of my life? What kind of social circle am I looking forward to? How am I feeling? How can I improve my mood? Well, with all of these questions in mind. That will produce several different emotions. For example, you may feel very entangled; you may think that you have broken the previous self-consistency, or you may feel that there is some tension.

Why is there a pulling feeling? It is because when we think more and more clearly, we may find some contradictions between individualism and traditional collectivism. In this process of contradictions, how should we choose? Should more personal thoughts be dropped? Or should we give up some ideas in some collectives or organizations? This is a tough choice. Because if I give up my thoughts, I will think more and more that my reflection is useless because I will not take action after consideration, and naturally, the change I want will not happen. Then if I feel more and more that my reflection is useless, I may stop self-reflection and stop genuinely being aware of my inner voice. As a result, it may lead to the accumulation of many emotions or the emergence of psychological problems, which is a slow process. Conversely, if I choose to give up the group idea, it will bring some consequences; for example, I may become less popular in the group, or other people in the group may think that I am not united enough and cooperative enough many more. Therefore, among all these contradictory choices or needs, many people need help finding a way to achieve both (unable to find a balance point).

In addition to the entanglement between individualism and collectivism, there is a common entanglement: self-consistency. After reflection, many people may find that my original practices may not be what I want. Or not who I am. It is just a model influenced by the original family or society. It is actually different from my real desire. So, next, I will face two choices. One choice is that I can change myself and follow my own heart more instead of being too influenced by the outside world and my native family. And what genetics has done to me. Another option is that I don't make any changes and continue to accept the influence of the outside world, the impact of my original family on me, and the influence of genetic factors on me, and not live out my true self.

Similarly, these two options will also bring some relatively contradictory psychology. Because if I decide to make a change, it means that I may have to get out of some of my original fundamental comfort zones, and getting out of the fundamental comfort zone itself will bring me a lot of uneasy feelings, or I will think it is very hard, or even say This is a very difficult journey and may require the support of some people, whether it is a good friend, family, or some professional counselors. Then another possibility is that I will continue to stay in my original model, not make any changes, and accept the influence of my original family, the influence of the outside world, and the influence of genetic factors on me. I don't think about what I want; I don't live the meaning of my life. However, there are also problems with this. The so-called lying down is just throwing all the problems into the subconscious level, and the issues will continue to accumulate, either at the subconscious level or the subconscious level. We will feel very restless, and our happiness in life will be very low. Or you have to constantly complain about why you don't live the way you want, and you may have a lot of inferiority complex, self-destructive, or other restless thoughts or even behaviors. Some people may then shirk their sense of responsibility for their own lives. Because I think that all the decisions in my life are made for others, I have sacrificed the possibility of my original life and the meaning of my life for the sake of the whole outside world. Therefore, you think that others cause everything you suffer or experience. This is also a very unhealthy behavior of shirking "responsibility for one's own life," which will reduce a person's self-efficacy or happiness.

To sum up, in the process of some stages of human development in today's society, there will be more desires for self-exploration, which may cause more psychological problems. That does not mean that society is regressing; on the contrary, society is progressing. People no longer live just to eat rice; people start to think more and find the meaning of life, which is a precious and meaningful process of human evolution. At the same time, it will naturally increase people's attention to psychological experience and optimization. But there is another very interesting phenomenon here. Many people may not have a mental illness; for example, they are not strictly diagnosed with obsessive-compulsive disorder, trauma, emergency response disorder, bipolar disorder, etc. Many people may only be in a state of sub-health mentally, that is to say, between full health and mental illness, in such a position, the third health or sub-health.

Under such a situation, in fact, many people who suffer from mental illness or are in a state of sub-health will not actively seek psychological treatment and counseling. The reasons for this are very complicated. For example, some people may still have some stereotypes, thinking that having a mental illness is very shameful; or some may feel that they do not want to spend time solving this problem because it is not as obvious and delays everyday life as physical illness. Of course, this is a kind of prejudice because psychological discomfort will interfere with a person's daily life and normal decisions to a great extent. Because it is everywhere, and psychological distress can lead to physical illness. The other type of people, those with sub-healthy mental health, will not seek psychological counseling or some psychological counseling in many cases. The reasons are also varied, for example, because of time; or because of fear of other people's eyes, or because they think that mental illness is not a disease and feel uncomfortable, and it will be fine after a while, so there is no need to be hypocritical; or some people maybe I don't have this budget for the time being, and I think that the consumption of psychology is very illusory, and I think that what can't be seen is meaningless, and what can be seen is meaningful.

All this will lead to many people being in a state of sub-health or mental illness. In such an environment, people will influence each other, which may cause more people to be infected with mental sub-health or mental illness. This is also a significant reason for researching this topic.

B. Research purpose and significance

Because of such a phenomenon in today's society, we need to intervene and supplement traditional psychological counseling in more interesting ways. Use a softer, more moisturizing, and even more "lifestyle" approach to help everyone achieve better mental health and improve the happiness of the whole society, which can bring many benefits: In addition to enhancing everyone's happiness, it can also improve everyone's sense of life experience, improve everyone's self-efficacy, and improve the productivity and security of the entire society. And art therapy is such a very good way.

Many people with mental sub-health and mental illness do not think that they have some specific psychological problems because they do not have the ability to identify them. There is a big difference between psychological problems and physical problems. In fact, many physical diseases cannot be distinguished. Except for trauma, there is actually no way to truly distinguish them accurately, but everyone knows that they will have some problems in this respect. Knowledge is limited, so when you feel unwell, you will seek professional help in time. Then when professionals give advice, patients will listen to these suggestions carefully and actively cooperate with treatment. Then mental sub-health is very different from physical diseases in this respect because they also feel uncomfortable, such as feeling uncomfortable, or low happiness, or anxiety and depression, but people will be too high. Suppose I assess my psychological level of cognition and knowledge. In that case, I will tend to think that I am apparent that this is not a problem or that I can solve it, so I miss the opportunity to receive professional guidance, guidance, or improve my happiness. . A more serious possibility is that it may eventually lead to some more serious mental illnesses.

So how to use a better way to improve the mental health of the whole people? Art is a very good way.

As mentioned at the beginning, in today's society, with the upward shift of Maslow's needs, people begin to pay more attention to some conditions in the spiritual field, so the pursuit of art is another manifestation of Maslow's upward shift in needs. Everyone starts to care more about non-material or non-functional attributes, and some things that can bring people a pleasant sense of experience, or even a vague sense of adventure, then art is undeniable of such things. Art exists in different forms, such as music, film, painting, photography, flower arrangement, etc.

Whether it is the process of creation or appreciation, art depends to a large extent on our inner and spiritual world. It needs you to listen, you need to imagine, you need to observe with empathy, and you need to Be patient and listen to your authentic inner voice. And these characteristics just mentioned are significantly related to psychological healing. Therefore, both the process of artistic creation and artistic aesthetics correspond to some psychological healing methods (such as humanistic therapy, Freudian therapy, Alfred therapy, logotherapy, etc.).

Another characteristic of art is that it is relatively separated from the conventional world. Because many people's job is not those of artist, the time to be exposed to art is relatively limited, especially the time to be exposed to art creation. Therefore, if people are allowed to start art therapy and produce some artistic creations in the process, it can be an excellent way to let customers get out of their daily life and do something impossible to do in everyday life. In this relatively different and calmer place, it is easier for people to jump out of the stereotyped thinking to be more aware of themselves instead of simply following the crowd or continuing the previous practice mechanically.

Through such a process, we can kill two birds with one stone. On the one hand, we can achieve some psychological healing effects. On the other hand, we can improve our life taste and artistic accomplishment, and even the spiritual level and personality charm of the whole person. Therefore, the combination of art and healing is a magical experience that kills two birds with one stone and even kills two birds with one stone.

CHAPTER TWO

THE LINK BETWEEN ART AND ART THERAPY

A. Definition of art

Art is a diverse range of human activities, and the resulting products involve creative or imaginative talents expressing technical proficiency, beauty, emotional power, or conceptual thought. [1] The arts are human beings' tools for cultivating distinctive social, cultural, and personal identities while transmitting values, impressions, judgments, thoughts, visions, spiritual meanings, life patterns, and experiences across time and space. Prominent examples of the arts include visual arts (including architecture, ceramics, painting, film-making, drawing, photography, and sculpture), literary arts (including fiction, drama, poetry, and prose), performing arts (including dance, music, and drama), and cooking Arts (including cooking, chocolate making, and winemaking). They can use skill and imagination to make objects, perform, communicate insights and experiences, and construct new environments and spaces. Art can refer to standard, popular, everyday practices or more complex, systematic, or institutionalized practices. They can be discrete and self-contained, or they can be combined and interwoven with other art forms, such as the combination of artwork and text in comics. They can also develop or promote certain aspects of more complex art forms, such as cinematography. Art itself, by definition, is open to being constantly redefined. For example, modern art practice demonstrates the changing boundaries, improvisation, experimentation, reflexivity, and self-criticism or questioning that art and its conditions of production, reception, and possibility can experience.

Art has served many functions throughout history, making its purpose difficult to abstract or quantify into any single concept. This doesn't mean that the purpose of art is "vague" but that it was created for many unique and different reasons. Some of Art's features are provided in the overview below. The other goals of art can be divided into groups according to unmotivated and motivated. [2]

The non-motivated purpose of art is to transcend the individual or to satisfy specific external goals. This type of artwork does not exist for some functional purpose. In other words, this kind of art is not intended for certain purposes, such as loading, bearing, eating, or keeping warm. The good or bad of this kind of creation cannot be evaluated by its practicality or even by its quality.

- Basic human instincts of harmony, balance, and rhythm. Art at this level is not an action nor a person; it is just inner appreciation and coordination (beauty). Therefore, it goes beyond practicality.
- Mystical experience. Art provides a way of experiencing oneself related to the universe. This experience may often arise automatically and unconsciously when a person appreciates art, music, or poetry.
- Expression of the imagination. Art provides a non-grammatical means of expressing imagination independent of the form of spoken or written language. Art provides a range of malleable forms, symbols, and ideas. The meaning contained in it varies in the ever-changing permutations and combinations.
- Ritual and symbolic functions. Art plays an important role in ritual, performance, and dance as decoration or symbol in many cultures. While they don't have a specific utilitarian goal, they are known to anthropologists and generally provide some reference to a different cultural meaning. This kind of meaning is not provided by anyone, it is usually changed by multiple generations, and it is also the result of a cosmological relationship that plays a role in culture. It is called intangible cultural heritage in many places.

The motives and goals of art are some initial sources of motivation for artists or creators, some of their visions that they hope to achieve, or some needs from customers. These purposes are very diverse; for example, they may originate from the artist, who has some ideas he wants to convey. Or the artist wants to create a specific work of art according to the client's needs, which may be painting, clothing design, architectural design, etc. It may also be some ideas produced by the artist based on some social conditions at that time, some social and psychological influences that the artist hopes to produce, or just some works that play a role in communication, or a bridge for communication, etc.

- Communicate. Art, at its simplest, is a form of communication. The art of illustration, such as scientific illustration, is an art form of communication. Maps are another example. However, the content does not have to be scientific. Emotions, moods, and feelings are also conveyed through art. [3]
- Art as entertainment. For example, we all go to the cinema to watch movies or play some mobile games or computer games. Or watch some MVs. Art may seek to bring about a particular emotion or mood, to relax or entertain the viewer. This is often a function of the art industries of movies and video games. [4]
- Avant-garde. The art of political change. For example, during the Renaissance period, there will be corresponding works of art during the Renaissance period. With every change in the political system or the upgrading of philosophical thoughts, some new art forms will be produced. It is even said that art preceded political change because it is a very important form of expression of changes in people's thinking.
- Art is a "free zone," detached from socially condemned actions. Unlike the avant-garde movement, which wants to eliminate cultural differences to produce new universal values, contemporary art enhances the tolerance of cultural differences and its critical and emancipatory functions (social inquiry, activism, subversion, deconstruction...) to become a more open place for research and experimentation.
- The art of social inquiry, subversion, or anarchy. At the same time, similar to the art of political change, subversive or deconstructive art may seek to question aspects of society without any specific political aim. In this case, the function of art may simply be to criticize certain aspects of society.
- The art of social enterprise. The arts can be used to raise awareness for a variety of causes. Many arts events aim to raise awareness about autism[5], cancer[6], human trafficking[7], and various other topics.
- Art for psychological and therapeutic purposes. Art is also used as art therapy by art therapists, psychotherapists, and clinical psychologists. For example, a diagnostic charting series is used to determine a patient's personality and emotional functioning. In this case, the end product is not the main goal but the process of seeking healing through creative acts. The resulting artwork could also provide insight into the troubles the subjects were experiencing and possibly suggest suitable treatment methods. [8]
- Propaganda art or commercialism. In both cases, the purpose of art is to subtly manipulate the viewer to produce a particular emotional or psychological response to a particular idea or object. For example, in consumer psychology, a large number of attributes of consumer psychology have been studied. Many art workers, or some related professionals, will also use some artistic means to attract the attention of consumers and use a relatively soft way to implant some beliefs for consumers or Plant an image of the brand in the minds of consumers.

B. Psychological healing and mental sub-health

➤ *Psychological healing*

Psychotherapy (also known as psychotherapy or talk therapy) is the use of psychological methods, especially when based on regular personal interaction, to help a person change behavior, increase well-being, and overcome problems. Psychotherapy aims to improve an individual's sense of well-being and mental health, address or alleviate troublesome behaviors, beliefs, compulsions, thoughts, or emotions, and improve interpersonal and social skills. [9] Many types of psychotherapy are designed for individual adults, families, or children and adolescents. There are hundreds of psychotherapy techniques, some with only very slight variations between them. A psychotherapist can be a mental health professional such as a psychiatrist, psychologist, mental health nurse, clinical social worker, marriage and family therapist, or professional counselor. Psychotherapists may also come from various other backgrounds and, depending on the jurisdiction, may be legally regulated, voluntarily regulated, or unregulated (and the term itself may or may not be protected).

Expressive psychotherapy is a branch of psychological healing that is closely related to art healing. Expressive psychotherapy is a form of therapy that utilizes artistic expression (through improvisation, creation, re-creation, and acceptance of experience) as a central means of treating clients. Expressive psychotherapists use different disciplines of creative arts as therapeutic interventions. This includes dance therapy, drama therapy, art therapy, music therapy, writing therapy, and more. [10] Expressive psychotherapists believe that the most effective way to treat clients is often through expressing the imagination in creative work and integrating and processing the issues raised in action.

In psychological healing, it is suggested that the people who must take psychological healing are:

- You have a hard time regulating your emotions. While we all feel sad, anxious, or angry at some point in our lives, it's important to pay attention to how often or intensely we feel these emotions. Example: Anger is often part of a depression presentation. In fact, in men, depression is often overlooked because their bad temper or irritability is mistakenly considered masculine.
- You are not doing well at work or school. Declining performance at work or school is a common sign for those struggling with mental or emotional problems. Mental health problems impair concentration, focus, memory, and energy and can lead to the apathy that diminishes enjoyment and even loss of motivation at work.
- You are experiencing changes or interruptions in sleep or appetite.
- You are struggling to form and maintain relationships.
- You have experienced trauma.
- You no longer enjoy the activities you normally do. People who struggle with mental or emotional problems often feel disconnected or alienated from life.
- You are sad. Whether it's a divorce, a major breakup, or losing a loved one, getting over any form of grief can be a long and painful process, especially if you have no one to share the emotional burden with.
- Your physical health has taken a hit. Mental health is linked to various physical health conditions, including headaches, fatigue, muscle aches and pains, greater cardiovascular response, weaker immune system, chronic inflammation, and more.
- You want to improve yourself and break out of negative patterns to activate more positive ones.
- You are coping with drugs or sex. Under mental or emotional stress, we turn to helpful, numbing, distracting, or destructive things to cope — which explains why substance use and sex are often used as coping mechanisms.

➤ *Mental sub-health*

The World Health Organization calls the state of the body without organic disease but some functional changes "the third state," and our country calls it a "sub-health state." The sub-health state can be defined as a state of physical examination characterized by the disturbance of psychological behavior, physical characteristics, or certain indicators without typical pathological features. People who are most prone to sub-health[11]:

- A person who is mentally overburdened;
- Those who are mentally heavy;
- People with heavy physical labor burdens;
- People with tense interpersonal relationships and heavy burdens;
- People who have been engaged in simple and mechanized work for a long time (lack of external communication and stimulation);
- Stressed person;
- A person whose life is irregular;
- People with an unbalanced diet, smoking and drinking.

With the sub-health mentioned above, we can see that among the eight easy-to-obtain characteristics of sub-health, more than 50% are related to human psychology. From this, we know that mental health and adjustment ability are important reasons that affect a person's overall health, sub-health, and disease state.

At the same time, in terms of the need for psychological treatment, the people who can receive psychological treatment are not only those diagnosed with mental diseases, such as PTSD, OCD, and depressive disorder but also many people who are mentally in sub-health (psychological behavior or physical health). Physical examination of a state characterized by symptoms or disorders of certain indicators without typical pathological features), such as:

- Depressed mood
- Better control one's emotions
- Optimize your intimacy
- Optimize your social circle
- Search for deep self-exploration and self-understanding
- Improve happiness level

C. How to improve the effectiveness of psychological healing through art

Art therapy incorporates methods of creative expression through the medium of visual arts. There are three main approaches to art therapy: The first is known as analytical art therapy. Analytical art therapy is based on theories from analytical psychology and, more commonly, psychoanalysis. Analytical art therapy focuses on the client, the therapist, and the ideas passed between the two of them through art. Another way to utilize art therapy is art psychotherapy. This approach focuses more on the psychotherapist and his verbal analysis of the client's artwork. A final way to look at art therapy is through the lens of art as therapy. Some art therapists in art therapy do not believe it is important to verbally analyze a client's artwork, so they emphasize the art-making process. In all of these different methods of art therapy, the art therapist's clients delve into their inner thoughts and emotions by using paint, paper, pencil, clay, sand, fabric, or other media.[12]

Art therapy can be used to help people improve cognitive and sensorimotor function, self-esteem, self-awareness, and emotional resilience. [2] It can also help resolve conflict and reduce suffering. Current art therapy includes a large number of other approaches, such as humanistic therapy, cognitive therapy, behavioral therapy, gestalt therapy, narrative therapy, and Adlerian therapy. The principles of art therapy include humanism, creativity, mediating emotional conflict, developing self-awareness, and personal growth.

The British Association of Art Therapists defines art therapy as: “a form of psychotherapy in which art media is the primary mode of expression and communication.” They also add that “clients referred to an art therapist do not need previous art experience; the art therapist is not primarily concerned with an aesthetic or diagnostic assessment of the client image.”[13]

Sometimes people can't express their feelings because it's hard to express them in words, and art can help people express their experiences. "During art therapy, people can use art as a way of coping with exploring past, present, and future experiences." [14] Using art therapy is also a great way for those with general ailments to express their feelings and emotions through art while explaining their feelings through words may or may not be very difficult. Art helps provide a sense of security for people's emotions if they are not comfortable sharing them with others but can trust the canvas or paper to hold them.

Regardless of artistic experience or talent, less than an hour of creative activity can reduce your stress and positively impact your mental health, according to a 2016 study published in the Journal of the American Art Therapy Association. [15]

CHAPTER THREE

CURRENT APPLICATION AND ANALYSIS OF ART THERAPY

A. *Types of Art Therapy*

The goal of art therapy is to use the creative process to help people explore self-expression and, in doing so, find new ways to gain personal insight and develop new coping skills. The creation or appreciation of art is used to help people explore emotions, develop self-awareness, cope with stress, improve self-esteem, and improve social skills.

Techniques used in art therapy can include:

- Collage
- Dyeing
- Graffiti And Graffiti
- Painting
- Dance Therapy
- Drama Therapy
- Music Therapy
- Writing Therapy
- Finger Painting
- Painting
- Photography
- Sculpture
- Use Clay

When clients create artwork, they may analyze their work and how it makes them feel. By exploring their art, people can look for themes and conflicts that may shape their thoughts, emotions, and actions. [16]

Areas of application in art therapy can include:

- Anxiety
- Cancer
- Depressed
- Eating Disorder
- Emotional Difficulties
- Family Or Relationship Issues
- Medical Condition
- Psychological Symptoms Associated With Other Medical Problems
- Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (Ptd)
- Psychosocial Problems
- Pressure
- Substance Use Disorder
- Aging

Scenarios used in art therapy can include:

- Art Studio
- Businesses And Organizations
- Colleges And Universities
- Community Center
- Juvenile Prison
- Elementary And High School

- Group Home
- Shelter
- Hospital
- Private Therapy Office
- Residential Treatment Center
- Senior Center
- Gym
- Women's Center

B. Application Status and Effect of Art Therapy

In today's society, Maslow's needs move up. People began to pay more and more attention to some individualistic questions, such as: Who am I? What is the purpose of my life? What kind of social circle am I looking forward to? How am I feeling? How can I improve my mood?

- Clients who face everyday challenges. Three studies have been conducted since 2008, two of which addressed issues of stress, distress, and burnout in individuals working in various health professions (Italia et al., 2008[17]; Visnola et al., 2010[18]). The studies were performed without randomization; in one study (Visnola et al., 2010[19]), there was a control group (level 2), while in the other study (Italia et al., 2008 [20]) (level 3). Sample sizes varied from 20 to 60 participants. The sessions lasted 9-13 sessions in a group art therapy setting. These studies suggest that art therapy can help healthcare professionals reduce levels of work-related stress, anxiety, and burnout.

Article Title	Author (year)	Sample (size and Group Description)	Intervention & Treatment	Amount and duration of therapy	Assessment Points	Outcome measured	Results
Evaluation and art therapy treatment of the burnout syndrome in oncology units.	Italia et al. (2008).	Only intervention group (N = 20)	Doctors and nurses from the Regional Reference Center for Pediatric Oncology at the University General Hospital.	Group meetings with the aim of increasing collaboration and relationships among the members of the curing team using the creative techniques of art therapy as a form of supportive and not psycho-therapeutic action.	The program was delivered 13 weekly meetings.	Baseline, immediately after.	The Masiach Burnout Inventory. Comparing the responses from participants before and after the intervention indicated a statistically significant decreased level of burnout. Level 3
Effects of art therapy on stress and anxiety of employees	Visnola et al. (2010)	N = 60 Intervention group (n = 30) Control group (n = 30)	Health care workers (women), ages 20-69.	The intervention group participated in an art therapy program consisting of three stages: 1) situation determination; 2) acquiring of methods of stress reduction and overcoming of anxiety; 3) awareness of self-conception and strengthening of potential (Visnola, 2009). The sessions were structured.	Nine sessions in total, 18 hours in two months.	Baseline, immediately after.	The Stress Questionnaire, the Spielberger examination of anxiety with State-trait Anxiety Inventory Form Y-1, the high performance liquid chromatography method (HPLC Water Alliance with UV detection) to establish levels of cortisol in saliva. Before and after art therapy in the experimental group, the level of the stress indicator (cortisol) over twenty-four hours and also the state of anxiety decreased significantly. The mean final stress level and situational anxiety for this group were significantly lower than for the control group. No significant changes were found for trait anxiety between groups. Level 2
A pilot study assessing art therapy as a mental health intervention for subfertile women	Hughes and da Silva (2011)	Only intervention group (N=21)	Women (Mean age = 35.7, S.D. = 2.1) attending the Hamilton Health Sciences fertility clinic for ongoing fertility care.	The eight group sessions were semi-structured and employed a different art therapy technique each week. Four to seven women per group.	Two-hour art therapy sessions once weekly, for 8 weeks.	Baseline, immediately after.	the Beck Anxiety Inventory, Beck Depression Inventory-II and Beck Hopelessness Scale Clinically and statistically significant reductions were seen in Beck Depression Inventory-II Scale and Beck Hopelessness Scale, while the change in Beck Anxiety score was not statistically significant. Level 3

Fig. 1: Clients Facing Daily Challenges Effectiveness of Art Therapy With Adult Clients in 2018—What Progress Has Been Made? Dafna Regev* and Liat Cohen-Yatziv School of Creative Arts Therapies, University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel

- Art therapy for mental health clients. Four studies have been conducted since 2007 (two articles were written on the same study - Crawford et al., 2012[21]; Leurent et al., 2014[22]). Such research falls into two main diagnostic areas. The first covered two studies of patients with schizophrenia (Richardson et al., 2007[23]; Crawford et al., 2012[24]; Leurent et al., 2014[25]) involving large samples (90-159 customers) randomization (level 1). The course of treatment ranges from 12 sessions to a full year of therapy, including group therapy. The various indicators used in these studies include measures of function, relationship, and symptoms. Despite attempts to use different types of research metrics, in both studies, little or no art therapy-related effects were found. Two studies were categorized as a second diagnostic domain: one in clients with psychiatric symptoms (Chandraiah et al. 2012[26]) (level 3) and one in women with depression (Thyme et al., 2007[27]) (Level 1). The course of treatment varies from 8 to 15 weeks. Results reported by two studies showed that the duration of the course of treatment changed. However, since neither study compared clients who received art therapy with those who did not, it was difficult to assess the effectiveness of art therapy. Thus, the cumulative results of such studies suggest that further research is needed to assess the effectiveness of art therapy interventions for clients dealing with mental health issues.

Article Title	Author (year)	Sample (size and groups)	Group Description	Intervention & Treatment	Amount and duration of therapy	Assessment Points	Outcome measured	Results
Exploratory RCT of art therapy as an adjunctive treatment in schizophrenia	Richardson et al. (2007)	N=90 Randomly assigned to Intervention group – Art Therapy (n = 43) Control group - standard psychiatric care (n = 47)	Adults patients – Intervention group – Mean age = 39.5; Control group – Mean age = 42.6. Diagnosis of chronic schizophrenia of at least two years' duration and excluding those: (i) with organic illness, (ii) with a prior referral to AT services in the previous 2 years, (iii) currently receiving another formal psychological treatment, or (iv) currently admitted to inpatient care.	Group interactive art therapy was conducted according to the guidelines set out in Waller (1993, pp. 22 – 34). Through the availability and use of art materials and associated imagery the therapist promotes a climate in which the service user can learn about and understand those patterns of behavior which are causing distress.	12 weekly sessions of one and a half hours.	Baseline, immediately after, and at 6-month follow-up.	General socio-demographic, clinical and health care utilization information, HONCIS Scales rated in collaboration with the CPN, Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS), Social Functioning Scale (SFS), Inventory of Interpersonal Problems (IIP-32), Scale for the Assessment of Negative Symptoms (SANS), Lancashire Quality of Life Profile (Perc CoL), Brief Symptom Inventory (BSI).	Art therapy produced a statistically significant positive effect on negative symptoms (assessed by Scale for the Assessment of Negative Symptoms) but had little and non-significant impact on other measures. Level 1
The outcome of short-term psychodynamic art therapy compared to short-term psychodynamic verbal therapy for depressed women	Thyme et al. (2007)	N = 39 Randomly assigned to Art psychotherapy (n=19) Verbal psychotherapy (n = 21)	Women with depression – aged 19-53 (Mean = 33.8).	Individual art psychotherapy	AT group – average of 15 weeks. VT group - average of 20 weeks.	Baseline, immediately after, 3-month follow-up.	The Impact of Event Scale (IES), The Symptom Check List 90 (SCL-90); Beck Depression Inventory (BDI); Hamilton Rating Scale of Depression (HRSD).	Participants in this study reported fewer depressive symptoms at the termination of psychotherapy compared to the initial level, and they reported even fewer symptoms at the 3-month follow-up. Observer-rated depressive symptoms showed a similar decline. The effect-sizes suggested a moderate to large change. The group variable did not contribute significantly to the analysis. Level 1
Efficacy of Group Art Therapy on Depressive Symptoms in Adult Heterogeneous Psychiatric Outpatients	Chandraiah et al. (2012)	Only intervention group – (N = 18) (Final sample - only 10 participants who attended 4 or more sessions)	Adult psychiatric outpatients aged 18-57 at a university medical center.	Group art therapy (8-8 in a group) - The beginning of each session was devoted to art making, usually 45-60 minutes, and the remaining 30 minutes was reserved for discussion.	8 sessions	Baseline, immediately after.	CES-D questionnaire - measures the level of depression experienced in the past week.	There was a statistically significant difference in the pre-treatment to post-treatment CES-D scores. Level 3
Group art therapy as an adjunctive treatment for people with schizophrenia: a randomized controlled trial (MATISSE)	Crawford et al. (2012)	N = 159 Randomly assigned to Intervention – art therapy (n=86) Control - activity groups attended at least one group (n = 73)	Adults aged 18 years or over (Mean = 41), had a clinical diagnosis of schizophrenia, confirmed by an examination of case notes.	Art therapy groups. Participants had up to eight members. Members were given access to a range of art materials and encouraged to use these to express themselves freely.	Weekly sessions of 90 min for an average period of 12 months.	Baseline, 12- and 24-month follow-up.	Completed by the researcher - Global functioning - using the GAF Scale, the Positive and Negative Syndrome (PANSS) Scale, Medication - using the Morsky Scale, the European Quality of Life-5 Dimensions (EQ-5D), the Adult Service Use Schedule (AD-SUS). Completed by the participant - the Social Function Questionnaire (SFO), the General Well-Being Scale, the Client Satisfaction Questionnaire (CSQ). Completed by the participants' key worker - the four-item Service Engagement Scale (SES). Data on occupational and housing status, Any incidents of suicidal behavior, Global functioning - using the GAF Scale, details of any period of inpatient treatment.	No differences in primary outcomes (12 months) were found. Differences in secondary outcomes were not found, except that those referred to an activity group had fewer positive symptoms of schizophrenia at 24 months than those randomized to art therapy. Level 1
Moderating factors for the effectiveness of group art therapy for schizophrenia: secondary analysis of data from the MATISSE randomized controlled trial	Leurent et al. (2014)						The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS), The Morsky scale, The Engagement and Acceptance Scale (EAS), Interview	The clinical effectiveness of group art therapy did not significantly differ between participants with more or less severe negative symptoms or between those who did and did not express a preference for art therapy. Level 1

Fig. 2: Mental Health Clients' Effectiveness of Art Therapy With Adult Clients in 2018—What Progress Has Been Made? Dafna Regev* and Liat Cohen-Yatziv School of Creative Arts Therapies, University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel

- Client post-traumatic art therapy. This study (Kopytin and Lebedev, 2013[28]) examined a sample of 112 veterans who had attended 12-14 art therapy sessions. In this study, traumatic events were more specifically defined and defined by participation in the war, so an attempt was also made to measure improvement across a broad range of research indicators, including symptom reporting, emotional state, and quality of life. Certain indicators improved significantly compared to the control group.

Article Title	Author (year)	Sample (size and groups)	Group Description	Intervention & Treatment	Amount and duration of therapy	Assessment Points	Outcome measured	Results
Humor, Self-Attitude, Emotions, and Cognitions in Group Art Therapy with War Veterans.	Kopytin and Lebedev (2013)	N = 112 Randomly assigned to Experimental group (n = 62) Control group (n = 50).	War Veterans aged 25-53 (Mean experimental group = 38; Mean control group = 35). The inclusion criteria were that participants had been diagnosed with having nonpsychotic mental disorders and had been involved in military campaigns. Patients were excluded from the study if they experienced severe mental disorders and were over 55.	Group sessions usually consisted of 5 to 8 patients. Each session was structured with warm-up activities, a main art- based activity with discussion, and closure.	Three times per week in after-lunch sessions that lasted 2.5 hours. The course of art therapy lasted one month and included 12 to 14 sessions.	Baseline, immediately after.	Symptomatic Checklists, SCL-90, Questionnaire of Depressive Conditions, the Integrative Anxiety Test, The self-report General Condition-Activity-Mood Test, The Silver Drawing Test (SDT) and Draw A Story assessment (DAS), The World Health Organization Quality of Life Questionnaire, The Humor scale.	When used as a brief intervention, group art therapy may exert a positive influence on war veterans and particularly on their symptomatic status, personality functioning, cognitive abilities and creativity and quality of life. Although these positive effects also were observed in the control group, they were less evident than in the experimental group. Scores on the DAS and SDT for emotional content, self-image, and cognition significantly increased for the experimental group after one month of art therapy; such increases were absent in the control group. Level 1

Fig. 3: Clients with PTSD Effectiveness of Art Therapy With Adult Clients in 2018—What Progress Has Been Made? Dafna Regev* and Liat Cohen-Yatziv School of Creative Arts Therapies, University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel

- For clients who lower their stress levels. Decreased cortisol levels and participant responses after art creation. An experimental study investigated the effects of visual art creation on cortisol levels in 39 healthy adults. Participants were provided saliva samples to assess cortisol levels before and after 45 minutes of art creation. Participants also provided written responses about the experience at the end of the session. The results showed that artistic creation resulted in significantly lower cortisol levels. Participants' written responses indicated that they found the art-making sessions relaxing, enjoyable, and helpful in understanding new aspects of the self, breaking free from constraints, and evolving from initial struggles to later resolutions. They also reflected that the meeting aroused a desire to make art in the future. [29]

Fig. 4: Mean salivary cortisol levels before (dark grey) and after (light grey) artistic creation.

Fig. 5: Individual salivary cortisol levels before (dark grey) and after (light grey) artistic creation

Making art is a pleasurable or relaxing experience for some. In contrast, for others, it is associated with freedom of expression, evokes a flow experience, inspires insight, and provides a way to learn about oneself. Further research is needed to better understand how these experiences relate to changes in cortisol levels and reduced stress.

- Extensive research on art therapy for prison inmates (Gussak, 2004[30], 2006[31], 2009a,b[32]). Since 2004, three effectiveness studies have been conducted in this area. The first examined the intervention group without a control group (level 3), while the other two studies did include a control group (level 2); the 2009 studies had sample sizes ranging from 48 to 247 participants. The art therapy intervention was conducted in a group setting and lasted four weeks in the first study and 15 weeks in the most recent study. Initially, Gussak used only measures of mapping (FEATS), but in later, more comprehensive studies, depression, and control points were also assessed. In three studies, art therapy interventions were reported to bring about improvements, as seen with prison inmates' emotional states.

Article Title	Author (year)	Sample (size and Group groups)	Group Description	Intervention & Treatment	Amount and duration of therapy	Assessment Points	Outcome measured	Results
Art therapy with prison inmates: A pilot study.	Gussak (2004)	Only intervention group (N = 48)	Male inmates aged 21-63 medium- to maximum-security,	Six groups of eight members - art therapy interventions developed from simple to complex and from individual art tasks to more interactive group projects.	Twice a week for 4 weeks.	Baseline, immediately after.	The Draw a Person Picking an Apple from a Tree evaluation - (FEATS), Survey - developed specifically for the pilot study by the primary investigator - seven categories focusing on the inmate's interactions and compliance with prison rules and expectations.	There was significant change in seven of the 14 scales of FEATS: Prominence of Color, Color Fit, Implied Energy, Space, Integration, Details of Objects, and environment and Line Quality. No results regarding the survey. Level 3
The effects of art therapy with prison inmates: A follow-up study.	Gussak (2006) -	N = 44 Intervention group (n = 27) Control group (n = 17)	Male Inmates aged 21 to 59.	Four groups - art therapy interventions developed from simple to complex and from individual art tasks to more interactive group projects.	Once a week for 8 weeks.	Baseline, immediately after.	The Draw a Person Picking an Apple from a Tree evaluation - (FEATS), The Beck Depression Inventory-Short Form (BDI-II).	BDI-II - The experimental group had significantly greater decrease from pretest to posttest than the control group. FEATS - The experimental group's rotation was greater than the control group's rotation. Level 2
The effects of art therapy on male and female inmates: Advancing the research base.	Gussak (2009a)	N = 247 Intervention group (n = 98 women + 75 men). Control group (n = 29 women + 45 men)	Inmates Intervention group - women - ages 25-51. Intervention group - men - ages 22-50.	Groups - art therapy interventions developed from simple to complex and from individual art tasks to more interactive group projects.	One session period lasted 15 weeks, one session per week.	Baseline, immediately after.	The Beck Depression Inventory-Short Form (BDI-II), the Adult Nowicki-Strickland Locus of Control Scale (ANS), The Draw a Person Picking an Apple from a Tree evaluation - (FEATS)	Overall, the results of the BDI-II and the ANS supported the hypotheses, while the FEATS did not. The results indicated a trend toward significance in a greater improvement in mood and internal locus of control in female inmates than male inmates. Level 2
Comparing the effectiveness of art therapy on depression and locus of control of male and female inmates.	Gussak (2009b)		Control group - women - ages 20-47 Control group - men - ages 24-51. Medium to maximum adult correctional facilities.					

Fig. 6: Clients of prison inmates Effectiveness of Art Therapy With Adult Clients in 2018—What Progress Has Been Made? Dafna Regev* and Liat Cohen-Yatziv School of Creative Arts Therapies, University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel

- Customers with medical conditions. The second category includes art therapy, where clients deal with a variety of medical conditions not related to cancer. Since 2011, three studies examining the effectiveness of art therapy have been conducted, each focusing on a completely different medical condition and using different research methods. The earliest research involved art therapy in patients with advanced heart failure (Sela et al., 2011[33]). The sample size for this study was 20 clients who were randomly divided into two groups (Level 1). The client participated in 6 weeks of group art therapy. A 2013 study performed art therapy on clients dealing with obesity (Sudres et al., 2013[34]). This study examined 170 clients who were randomly divided into two groups (Level 1). One group consisted of 96 clients who underwent art therapy for two weeks. A 2014 study performed art therapy on 25 HIV/AIDS patients (Feldman et al., 2014[35]) who received art therapy in an individual or group setting, excluding a control group (level 3). The duration of a course of treatment is one or more sessions. Despite considerable variability between populations and measured indices, these preliminary studies provide an introductory description pointing to the potential of art therapy to help these populations.

Article Title	Author (year)	Sample (size and groups)	Group Description	Intervention & Treatment	Amount and duration of therapy	Assessment Points	Outcome measured	Results
The influence of medical art therapy on quality of life and compliance of medical treatment of patients with advanced heart failure	Sela et al. (2011)	N = 20 Randomly assigned to Intervention group - Art Therapy (n = 10) Control group - routine clinical visit only (n = 10).	Patients with advanced heart failure.	A medical art therapist guided group A to express their feelings using art materials.	Met weekly for 8 weeks (First and last visits were individual, 6 group meetings).	Baseline, immediately after.	The Ulman, (a MAT diagnostic tool), the Minnesota Living with HF and compliance questionnaires.	Baseline Ulman, compliance and Minnesota scores were similar for the two groups. By the end of the study, the Ulman score improved significantly in the AT group compared to the control group as did the compliance score. In the AT group, the Minnesota score improved significantly in 7 patients and did not change in 3, while in the control group it improved in 2, did not change in 6 and worsened in 2. Level 1
Therapeutic patient education with art therapy: Effectiveness among obese patients	Sudres et al. (2013)	Randomly assigned to N = 170 AT (n = 74) Group 1 - without Group 2 - with AT (n = 96)	Obese patients. Group 1 - Mean age=54.4 Group 2- Mean age = 54.5 The exclusion criteria were the following: diabetes, personality disorder diagnosis, presence of any antipsychotic or personality disorder requiring treatment, and the use of non-stabilized antidepressant or anti-anxiety treatment in the last 6 months.	Structured AT session workshops.	5 sessions, 2 hours each, over 2 weeks	Baseline, at the beginning of TPE program before the AT sessions (T0), after the two-week TPE program (T1) and at follow-up 6 weeks after the end of the TPE program (T2).	Torrance Tests of creative Thinking (TTCT), The Clinical Scale of Mediatized Therapies.	Significant weight loss was observed in both groups after 6 weeks following the TPE program. Group 2 subjects receiving art therapy showed an increase in quantitative indicators of creativity as well qualitative indicators as compared to Group 1 without AT. However, Group 1 without AT displayed a consistent reduction in all quantitative and qualitative indicators of creativity during and after the TPE program. Level 1
Process and Outcome Evaluation of an Art Therapy Program for People Living With HIV/AIDS	Feldman et al. (2014)	Only intervention group (N=25)	Adults living with HIV/AIDS - Mean age = 44.1, did not receive art therapy services prior to the baseline assessment.	Attended one or more individual or group art therapy sessions or open studio sessions.	One or more sessions.	Baseline and 6-month follow-up.	Depression Severity - The Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9), The clients' health-related quality of life -The Short Form Health Survey (SF-12).	Statistically significant changes from baseline to 6-month follow-up in the desired direction were observed for both of the primary outcomes. Level 3

Fig. 7: Healthcare related customers Effectiveness of Art Therapy With Adult Clients in 2018—What Progress Has Been Made? Dafna Regev* and Liat Cohen-Yatziv School of Creative Arts Therapies, University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel

- Art therapy for cancer patients. Since 2006, six studies examining validity in this specific population have been performed and described in seven different articles (Monti et al., 2006[36], 2012[37]; Oster et al., 2006[38]; Öster et al., 2007[39]; Bar-Sela et al., 2007[40]; Svensk et al., 2009[41]; Thyme et al., 2009[42]). Five of the six studies were randomized (level 1), and five involved women, most of whom had breast cancer. The total sample size ranged from 18 to 111 clients, most of whom were treated individually. Most treatment sessions are short-term, ranging from five to eight sessions. Several studies have utilized different streams of art therapy. For example, the largest study (Monti et al., 2006[43]) with 111 participants included a mindfulness-based art therapy intervention—a combination of art therapy and mindfulness exercises. The studies measured very differently, including questionnaires examining physical symptoms, coping resources, quality of life, depression, anxiety, and fatigue. A specific study (Monti et al., 2012[44]) also involved fMRI measurements. Findings in this category suggest that it is possible to significantly improve the emotional state and perceived symptoms of these clients with relatively short-term interventions in art therapy, primarily individual sessions.

Article Title	Author (year)	Sample (size and groups)	Group Description	Intervention & Treatment	Amount and duration of therapy	Assessment Points	Outcome measured	Results
A randomized, controlled trial of mindfulness-based art therapy (MBAT) for women with cancer	Monti et al. (2006)	N = 111 Randomly assigned to Mindfulness-based Art Therapy (MBAT) Intervention (n = 56) Wait list control group (n = 55)	Women diagnosed with cancer. Each subject was between four months and two years of an original diagnosis of cancer (or remission). Patients were excluded if they were terminal, or had a current psychiatric diagnosis of a major mood disorder, psychotic disorder, or significant cognitive deficits as determined by their physicians.	MBAT - a supportive-expressive group therapy that includes skills training in mindfulness meditation and group art therapy tasks.	The intervention consisted of eight consecutive weekly meetings of two and a half-hours each. Home assignments included the practice of mindfulness meditation 6 days a week for 30min	Baseline and post-intervention (at weeks 8 and 16).	The Symptoms Checklist Revised (SCL-90-R), The Global Severity Index (GSI), The Medical Outcomes Study Short-Form Health Survey (SF-36).	As compared to the control group, the MBAT group demonstrated a significant decrease in symptoms of distress (as measured by the Symptoms Checklist-90-Revised) and significant improvements in key aspects of health-related quality of life (as measured by the Medical Outcomes Study Short-Form Health Survey). Level 1
Art therapy improves coping resources: A randomized, controlled study among women with breast cancer	Oster et al. (2006)	N = 41 Randomly assigned to Intervention group (n = 20) Control group (n=21)	Women aged 37-69 (Median = 59) with non-metastatic primary breast cancer, referred to the Department of Oncology at Umeå University Hospital in Sweden for postoperative radiotherapy.	Individual art therapy intervention.	Five sessions, one hour each.	Baseline (start of radiotherapy) and 2 and 6 months after baseline.	Interviews, Diaries, Coping Resources Inventory (CRI).	There was an overall increase in coping resources among women with breast cancer after taking part in the art therapy intervention. Significant differences were found between the experimental and control groups in the social domain on the second and third occasions. Significant differences were also observed in the total score on the second occasion. The results showed a connection between participation in art therapy, talking about protecting one's own boundaries, and scoring higher on the CRI compared to the control group. There was also an association between the control group, repertoire conflicts, and lower scores on the CRI. Level 1
Art therapy for women with breast cancer: the therapeutic consequences of boundary strengthening	Oster et al. (2007)							
Art therapy improved depression and influenced fatigue levels in cancer patients on chemotherapy	Bar-Sela et al. (2007)	N=60 Intervention group - patients who participated in 4 sessions or more (n = 19) participant group - patients who participated in 2 sessions or less (n = 41)	Cancer patients aged 25-72 (Median=55) receiving chemotherapy.	The art therapists instructed each patient personally every week (Anthroposophical art therapy - painting with water-based paints). The sessions took place in a small room with eight workstations which was the maximum capacity for working with patients at the same time.	A variable amount of sessions - Once-weekly art therapy sessions. The patient chose how long to spend in the session, from a few minutes to more than an hour.	Before every session, relating to the previous week.	Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) and the Brief Fatigue Inventory (BFI).	BFI scores were significantly higher in the participant group. In the intervention group, the median HADS score for depression was 9 at the beginning and 7 after the fourth appointment (significant difference). The median BFI score went from 5.7 to 4.1 (Non-significant). The anxiety score was in the normal range from the beginning. Level 2
Art therapy improves experienced quality of life among women undergoing treatment for breast cancer: a randomized controlled study	Svensk et al. (2009)	N = 41 Randomly assigned to Intervention group (n = 20) Control group (n = 21)	Women -control- Median age=55 Intervention -Median age = 59.5 undergoing radiotherapy treatment for breast cancer.	Individual art therapy sessions.	Five sessions, one hour each.	Baseline (start of radiotherapy) and 2 and 6 months after baseline.	WHOQOL-BREF and EORTC Quality of Life Questionnaire-BR23	The results indicated an overall improvement in QoL aspects among women in the intervention group. A significant increase in total health, total QoL, physical health and psychological health was observed in the art therapy group. A significant positive difference within the art therapy group was also seen concerning future perspectives, body image and systemic therapy side effects. Level 1
Individual brief art therapy can be helpful for women with breast cancer: A randomized controlled clinical study	Thyme et al. (2009)	N = 41 Randomly assigned to Intervention group (n = 20) Control group (n = 21)	Women aged 37-69 with breast cancer. Exclusion criterion was a preexisting physical or psychiatric illness.	The intervention in this study provided the participants with five individual sessions of art therapy where they were encouraged to express their feelings and thoughts.	Five sessions, one hour each.	Baseline (start of radiotherapy) and 2 and 6 months after baseline.	Structural Analysis of Social Behavior - The SASB, Symptom Check list-90 The SCL90.	The hierarchical regression analyses suggested that art therapy was related to lower ratings of depression, anxiety, and somatic symptoms, as well as a lower level of general symptoms. Level 1
Changes in cerebral blood flow and anxiety associated with an 8-week mindfulness programme in women with breast cancer	Monti et al. (2012)	N = 18 Randomly assigned to Mindfulness-based Art Therapy (MBAT) (n = 8) Education control group (n = 10)	Women aged 52-77 who had been diagnosed with breast cancer between 6 months and 3 years prior to enrollment and were not in active treatment.	MBAT - a supportive-expressive group therapy that includes skills training in mindfulness meditation and group art therapy tasks.	Eight consecutive, weekly meetings of two and a half hours each in length.	Baseline, immediately after.	The fMRI imaging protocol consisted of five perfusion fMRI (using ASL) scans performed with a fixed order: 'Resting 1, Neutral task (i.e. control), Meditation task (Body Scan), Stressor task, and Resting 2'. The response to the programme was evaluated utilizing the Symptom Checklist-90-Revised (SCL-90-R) as a behavioral rating.	Subjects in the MBAT group demonstrated significant increases in CBF (blood supply to the brain in a given period of time) at rest and during meditation in multiple limbic regions, including the left insula, right amygdala, right hippocampus and bilateral caudate. Patients in the MBAT programme also presented a significant correlation between increased CBF in the left caudate and decreased anxiety scores. In the MBAT group, responses to a stressful cue resulted in reduced activation of the posterior cingulate. The results indicated that the MBAT programme was associated with significant changes in CBF, which correlated with decreased anxiety over an 8-week period. Level 1

Fig. 8: Effectiveness of Art Therapy With Adult Clients in 2018—What Progress Has Been Made? Dafna Regev* and Liat Cohen-Yatziv School of Creative Arts Therapies, University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel

- Art therapy for older adults. Three efficacy studies have been conducted since 2006: one in healthy older Korean American adults (Kim, 2013), the second in older adults coping with depression (McCaffrey et al., 2011), The third is for older adults with moderate to severe dementia (Rusted et al., 2006). In all three studies, participants were randomized into groups (Level 1) with sample sizes of 39-50 clients in a group therapy setting. The number of sessions varies from 6 to 40. The authors of these studies are interested in various indices. In a study of Korean older adults and older adults coping with depression, various aspects of clients' emotional states were measured. Art therapy is thought to have led to improvements in these measures. In a study of people with dementia, many observational measures were used to assess emotional state, behavior, and ability, but changes were found in only some of them. Findings suggest that art therapy appears to have beneficial effects on older adults coping with various life challenges, as reflected in the changes in the indices in these studies.

Article Title	Author (year)	Sample (size and groups)	Group Description	Intervention & Treatment	Amount and duration of therapy	Assessment Points	Outcome measured	Results
A Multi-center Randomized Control Group Trial on the Use of Art Therapy for Older People with Dementia	Rusted et al. (2006)	N = 45 Randomly assigned to art therapy or activity groups.	Patients Women – ages 74-92 (Mean=84.05) Men – ages 67-92 (Mean=80.33) diagnosed with mild to severe dementia. Inclusion criteria were diagnosis of dementia (mixed origin), attendance at day care or residential facility, previous diagnosis by consultant psychogeriatrician, confirmatory diagnosis from medical records. Exclusion criteria were additional psychiatric disorders.	Art therapy or activity groups (with a maximum of six participants per group). For the art therapy groups, a group-interactive, psychodynamic approach was employed.	One hour each week for 40 successive weeks.	Six assessment points - (at baseline, ten, 20 and 40 weeks into group work, with one and three months follow-up).	Cornell Scale for Depression in Dementia (CSDD), The Multi Observational Scale for the Elderly (MOSES), The Mini-Mental State Exam (MMSE), The Rivermead Behavioral Memory Test (RBMT), Tests of Everyday Attention (TEA), Benton Fluency Task, Bond-Lader Mood Scale, Skill Builders, Clifton Assessment Procedures for the Elderly (CAPE), the Rating Scale for Aggressive Behaviour in the Elderly.	This research provided clear evidence of positive and durable benefits in aspects of mental alertness, sociability, physical and social engagement in clients with moderate and severe dementia. These changes were quantitatively different from the pattern of effects achieved with a parallel programme of recreational activity. Level 1
Garden walking and art therapy for depression in older adults: a pilot study	McCaffrey et al. (2011)	N = 39 Randomly assigned to Art Therapy (n=13) Group Walking/ Guided Imagery (n=13) Independent Walking (n=13)	Art Therapy – Mean age= 74.30 (S.D.=6.4) Group Walking/ Guided Imagery Mean age=74.60 (S.D.=4.98) Independent Walking – Mean age 73.90 (S.D.=6.79) Inclusion criteria were that participants had self-diagnosed or health care provider-diagnosed depression, were able to walk approximately 1 mile, were older than 65, and could get to the gardens twice per week for 6 weeks.	The art therapy group met with a certified art therapist. This group began by drawing a self-portrait and presenting their portrait to the entire group. New drawings and discussions took place each week. The independent and guided garden walking groups met on different days at the gardens. Participants in the walk alone group signed in and walked the garden alone.	6 weeks. The art therapy group met twice per week.	Baseline, immediately after.	Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS), <i>Positive- and Negative-Emotion Word Use</i> .	Significant decreases were found in depression for all three groups from pretest to posttest. No significant differences were noted between the groups over time. Pos-itive-emotion word use increased and negative-emotion word use decreased. Regardless of intervention group, groups did not differ over time. Level 1
A randomized, controlled study of the effects of art therapy on older Koreans' healthy aging	Kim (2013)	N = 50 Randomly assigned to group A, the art therapy intervention group (AG) (n= 21 women and 4 men). Group B, the control group (CG) (n= 18 women and 7 men) Later, assigning them to each group (AG or CG) alternately.	Korean American older individuals – AG- ages 69-87 (Mean=77.64, S.D.=5.51) CG – ages 72-86 (Mean=78.76, S.D.=4.02). From two adult day health care programs (ADHCP)	The structure of the art therapy intervention was based on the psycho-cybernetics approach to art therapy (Nucho, 2003). Each session consisted of 10-15 min for introduction as an "unfreezing" phase, 35-40min for individual art-making as a "doing and dialoging" phase, and 15-20 min for group discussion as an "ending and integrating" phase	AG - 4 weeks of art therapy at a frequency of three times per week (for a maximum of 12 sessions). The total session time was 60-75 min.	Baseline, immediately after.	The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS), the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES).	Participants in the AG showed a greater change on the PANAS in a positive direction compared to the CG; Participants in the AG reported a greater decrease in both state and trait anxiety after the art therapy intervention compared to those in the CG; Participants in the AG showed a greater increase in self-esteem after the intervention compared to those in the CG; Level 1

Fig. 9: Elderly customers Effectiveness of Art Therapy With Adult Clients in 2018—What Progress Has Been Made? Dafna Regev* and Liat Cohen-Yatziv School of Creative Arts Therapies, University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel

C. Quantitative and qualitative analysis of art therapy user feedback

The author takes art therapy as a training topic in daily practical work and applies it to organizational training. The following are the feedback reports obtained from several topics, including some quantitative analysis content, including ratings given by customers and Satisfaction; it also includes some qualitative analysis, which comes from some personal feelings of customers after application.

➤ Caseone:

The author takes art therapy as a training topic in daily practical work and applies it to organizational training. The following are the feedback reports obtained from several topics, including some quantitative analysis content, including ratings given by customers and Satisfaction; it also includes some qualitative analysis, which comes from some personal feelings of customers after application.

Break the traditional society's definition of an artist. Teach everyone the basic principles of artistic aesthetics, encourage everyone to create their art, and express some true inner emotions in such a way. Because the source of artistic creation is the inner emotion, whether it is joy, anger, sorrow, joy, harmony, or conflict, it is a very important motivation and source of artistic creation. There is no creation without emotion. I create my own works of art based on some of my current feelings, some emotions accumulated in my heart over some time, or even some of my own perceptions of inward exploration throughout my life. The forms of works created by each person are different, covering a very wide variety of art healing types, such as painting, photography, sculpture, clip art, coloring, etc. (N=12)

Fig. 10: Satisfaction with the services of art therapy coach trainers

Fig. 11: Satisfaction with the contents and effects of art therapy

Participant Feedback on Participation Experience:

- Through this experience, I was able to withdraw from my usual life and enter the art world. This world is very different from the world I usually live in. It allows me to temporarily withdraw from the usual stereotyped thinking, quietly listen to my true inner thoughts in another world, explore other people's emotions and myself in art. emotions and come to terms with myself. (an enterprise manager)
- ✓ I am very happy to be able to create my own artwork for the first time. It turns out that works of art are made of emotions, and it is because of feelings in the heart that we can create our own unique works of art. I was so excited when I saw my first artwork. I didn't expect that there would be so many emotions in my heart waiting to be vented, and I didn't expect that my artwork could be so creative beyond my own imagination of myself. During this process, I fully released myself and fully recognized myself. (an enterprise manager)
- ✓ Although there are many constraints and objective conditions in real life, many times, we cannot completely follow our hearts. However, during the experience of art healing, you can fully listen to your own thoughts, create according to your own wishes, and complete your work. And this work is completely my own, a unique work full of my own personality; I think the whole process is very vivid; I entered the state of flow. Let me find a pure land, and in this pure land, I am absolutely safe. It is a magical experience to not only increase your sense of experience and enjoyment but also increase self-awareness and learn new knowledge to improve happiness. (an enterprise manager)

➤ Case two:

The author held an event on art therapy to release the stress generated by the participants at work. These participants are all relatively high-achieving people in their jobs. Such excellent results have also caused them to have a lot of pressure at work. For a long time, the backlog of pressure needs to be released, so the author chose the way of art healing to cultivate everyone's sentiment and improve everyone's taste while healing everyone's heart and releasing everyone's pressure. Let everyone's psychology become more comfortable, and the happiness degree has been greatly improved. In art healing activities, everyone can not only create art. More importantly, everyone can also give speeches and share their own creations. Everyone will fully listen to each other, and everyone's work can be purchased by everyone else. This feeling of listening to each other and being recognized by each other is an innovative way of art therapy. (N1=44, N2=43)

Fig. 12: Satisfaction with the services of art therapy coach trainers (N1=44)

Fig. 13: Satisfaction with the contents and effects of an therapy (N1=44)

Fig. 14: Satisfaction with the services of art therapy coach trainers (N2=43)

Fig. 15: Satisfaction with the content and effect of art therapy (N2=43)

Participant Feedback on Participation Experience:

- This experience was very healing for me, and it relieved a lot of my stress as if a lot of burdens had been lifted, and I could go on the road easily again.
 - ✓ The whole art creation process made me feel very wonderful, and then I also had my own first artwork full of my own ideas.
 - ✓ In this art journey, I have explored a lot of emotions, and these emotions are positive emotional energy.
 - ✓ This is a very new experience, and I feel novelty and sublimation.
 - ✓ I am very grateful for this experience and very moved. When my work is recognized by everyone and purchased, I feel that my whole person has also been recognized.
 - ✓ Full of novelty in exploring new knowledge and fields.
 - ✓ Rebirth, love, confidence.
 - ✓ Vision, Motivation, and the original appearance in life are the best appearance.

➤ Case three:

Service user perspectives on art therapy experiences from clients of Creative Therapies Service in Exeter. [45] Art therapy is a form of psychotherapy in which art is the medium of expression and communication. In this case, art is not used as a diagnostic tool but rather as a medium to address emotional issues that can be confusing and distressing. Art therapists work with children, young adults, adults, and the elderly. Clients may have various difficulties, disabilities, or diagnostic issues. These include emotional, behavioral, or mental health problems, learning or physical disabilities, life-limiting illnesses, neurological disorders, and physical illnesses.

Art therapy is administered in groups or individually, depending on the client's needs. It's not entertainment, and it's not art class, although classes can be fun. Customers do not need to have any experience or specialties in art.

Although in psychoanalysis, art therapists have been inspired by attachment psychotherapy and other theories and have been widely used in psycho-education, mindfulness and psychotherapy, compassion and cognitive analysis therapy, and social participation practice. In some of the BAAT conferences, the relationship between neuroscience and art therapy was discussed, always at the forefront. The point is that art therapy practice has become an important part of corporate culture and social diversity.

Participant Feedback on Participation Experience:

- "I've had a lot of benefits... really lasting benefits that I've been able to take on on my own, like a new way of doing things and a different way of coping. I think I've gotten more out of it than I thought possible ."
- ✓ "I really feel like it's given me more tools to deal with the things I need to deal with."
- ✓ "It's had a profound impact. I think it's the most successful thing I've done in the history of mental health. I've taken what I was doing there and used it."
- ✓ "I don't feel like a prisoner of depression anymore. I can't tell you what that means. I'd rather die than go through another dark period like the last one. But it's given me a new way of being to show a different way of coping."
- ✓ "The way I'm coping now has changed dramatically. I don't think realistically I can expect more."
- ✓ "I have had profound and lasting benefits from this work."

CHAPTER FOUR

APPLICATION PROSPECTS OF ART THERAPY

A. Application in adult corporate training and adult coaching

Just because adults have more language experience than children doesn't necessarily mean they're better at understanding their emotions and telling others what they're going through. Often, when dealing with adult issues, it's more difficult to articulate what hurt and why. Moreover, the expressions of adults often lack candor or transparency. The reason is that everyone has become accustomed to not telling the whole story about many things and not telling the complete truth about many things. Because everyone will have a lot of privacy and have a lot of difficulties, or many people may think that speaking out will make them very vulnerable. And all of this will make it even more difficult for adults to pay attention to psychological problems than teenagers.

Then in the face of such difficulties, art therapy can play a very good role. Because art healing is a selective way of expression, everyone can express all their emotions through the form of artistic creation but increase their own psychological observation, and the results of this observation can be expressed and fully revealed, can also be expressed selectively. However, no matter whether it is fully shared with the outside world or not, it will not affect the exploration and communication between customers and themselves as transparently as possible in the process. Another way is through artistic aesthetics rather than artistic creation. There are 10,000 Hamlets in 10,000 people's hearts, and the reason is that each of us sees everything through our own hearts. Through the matter of artistic aesthetics, it can help everyone to be more aware of what is thinking in their hearts. Because we will find that if we don't recite some comments, then, under normal circumstances, everyone's understanding of the same work of art is very different. The differences in these details reflect the differences in the psychological state of each of us, the differences in personal preferences, and the differences in the meaning we pursue. At the same time, in the process of artistic aesthetics, we can also cultivate and strengthen the ability to empathize with customers because art aesthetics requires you to enter the world of the creator of the artwork, trying to figure out what the artist wanted to express at that time. This requires us to look at the problem from a different angle and to put ourselves in the situation to generate some thinking. If we provide some background on the original author's life, then everyone can empathize with his life experience more, use empathy to understand the situation he was in at that time, the reason for his creation, and his What is the state of mind that artistic creation wants to express? Through such an empathy practice, we can improve everyone's empathy and help everyone get out of their own world for a while. Stepping out of one's own obsession can alleviate many mental sub-health problems.

Art therapy can also play the role of sand table or inkblot psychology. We can open each other's hearts through some diverse art media and understand more about what issues the other party is thinking about at the moment. Because art as a whole is the expression of emotions, the same scene outlined by each person through different emotions, or the same character to perform, will show completely different characteristics, and this characteristic is full of many psychological projections. Art is a medium that does not lie relatively because the source of his creation comes from rich emotions and inner thinking.

In today's society and in the future workplace needs, the abilities that most personnel need to possess are not only professional knowledge corresponding to disciplines and majors but also some soft skills. Among the soft skills, there are countless related to psychology, such as:

- Leadership
- Management
- How To Coach Employees
- How To Empower Employees
- How To Improve The Protagonist Awareness Of Everyone On The Team

- Insight Into Consumer Psychology
- Effective Marketing Plan
- Service Design
- Artificial Intelligence
- Customer Satisfaction
- Employee Satisfaction
- Talent Development
- Talent Selection And Retention

All of this is related to psychology, which requires decision-makers and even front-line employees of all enterprises to have a rich knowledge of psychology so that everyone can be guaranteed to be better competent in their positions. Art therapy is a very good tool to get started, leading everyone to improve personal happiness, help improve team efficiency, and also help improve operating efficiency, making the development of the entire enterprise or organization more sustainable. In addition, among team-building activities, art therapy activities and other psychological activities are more effective and in-depth than traditional team-building activities. Because traditional team-building activities are more about highlighting the role of mutual support in external behaviors. They are relatively simple entertainment or physical game activities that do not bring out the deepest part of people's hearts.

Answering some doubts or sharing some deepest ideas, so cannot fundamentally increase the trust between the teams or bring some more positive influences on the way everyone does things in the future.

To sum up, whether it is coaching for executives, training for all employees, or even team building between departments, a large number of art therapy or other forms with a richer psychological background can be introduced to improve the quality of a family. The happiness of the enterprise or organization, improving the efficiency of teamwork, improving engagement, and improving employee satisfaction. Make an organization or company more sustainable to release its potential in personnel management and performance management.

B. Use in adolescents

A major achievement in adolescent development is the formation of identities, which form the basis for adolescents' beliefs, values, and social understanding of their roles in society.

The development of this identity can be influenced by many factors, both positive and negative. The impact of negative influences can be damaging to teens and lead them down a life path shaped by false beliefs about their personal worth. These negative effects may include intergenerational trauma, family breakdown, parenting/carers, school difficulties, and exclusion from peers.

Even for adolescents who experience primarily positive influences during adolescence, the tension that exists in forming an identity can feel like an identity crisis, as adolescents are often forced to assess their place within the family and social peer groups. Teenagers are deeply influenced by their peers and the way they think they are perceived by their peers. This often means that teens are reluctant to admit that they need help with issues they feel may be viewed as weaknesses by their peers.

The stages of development that teens go through put them in a vulnerable stage. In this regard, art therapy can play an important role in helping teens explore their identities in their social circles.

During the teenage years, teens are still developing verbal expressions and how to interpret their evolving ideas. Adolescence is a sometimes confusing time when individuals are formalizing their beliefs about themselves, their families, and the ways they resolve conflict in their lives. The conflict between developing beliefs and the inability to express beliefs can be a problem for adolescents.

It can be a frustrating experience. Psychosocial problems are very common among children and adolescents, with an estimated global prevalence of 10%-20%. [46] Art therapy can help teens explore this process and provide a visual outlet for their thoughts when words are not readily available.

During the teenage years, teens are also developing an understanding of their emotions, like what are emotions? How to manage emotions? How do emotions trigger the behavior? Along with self-exploration, however, teens are often exposed to external pressure from parents, peers, and other authority figures.

Art therapy helps teens solve problems, enhance self-esteem, build social skills, and manage behavior. Whatever the art medium for art therapy, it can play an important role in the progress of teenage clients. Art therapy activities can help relieve stress, build connections, and encourage self-esteem, especially among young people. In therapy, all of these issues are top concerns for many clinicians, and art healing activities can be an effective way to connect with teenage clients. Art therapy activities often focus on the visual arts, such as painting, photography, and sculpture. But creativity is not limited to the visual arts. Some clients may feel uncomfortable drawing or painting if they are not skilled in these areas. Expressive arts therapy also incorporates other forms of creativity -- such as poetry, music, dance, and even theater -- into therapy. On a deeper level, art actually seems to have an effect on the brain's neural connections that serve as the wiring for learning. Regardless of the art form employed, the senses must function, and it requires deep thought. This leads to the development of skills such as recognizing the difference between abstraction and reality, understanding patterns, observing the world, and forming mental representations of things, real or imagined. Overall, expressive arts help children develop comprehensive thinking skills through the interaction of complex thought processes.

The art therapist's neutral stance can lead to trust, which is the foundation of any kind of therapeutic relationship. This principle of neutrality must be established from the beginning of the art therapy relationship. Art therapists don't see the magic of meaning in art; the "magic" comes from the creativity of teens [47]. The evaluation is done by comparing art products one by one and flagging changes in the art content and the client's verbal interpretation of its meaning.

Using art in therapy provides a pleasure factor that fuels their desire to express themselves. Drawing or marking is consistent with adolescent development, as evidenced by the abundance of marking and graffiti in many cities. It's hard to resist the urge to "make your mark" as a teenager. Channeling this drive into productive communication can defuse teens' mental battles about whether or not to share. The emergence of images is an extension of the memory and conceptualization process. Imagery introduces the metaphorical language and personalizes communication. Clinical art therapy may be effective for adolescents who typically view it as a non-threatening form of therapy. Art created by teens can help therapists understand teens' concerns and life circumstances, especially those that are too risky to reveal or personally embarrassing to relate to. This awareness better equips therapists in their efforts to protect and support teens during this turbulent time in their lives. Art therapists work from different directions and theories, such as psychodynamic; humanistic (phenomenological, gestalt, person-centered); psycho-educational (behavioral, cognitive-behavioral, developmental); systemic (family and group therapy); and compromise approaches. Also, there are various differences in the individual preferences and orientations of art therapists (Van Lith, 2016) [48]. During art healing, art therapists can promote positive change in psychosocial issues through exposure to the therapist and art materials in a fun and safe environment. Mental health optimization for adolescents provides effective positive outcomes. [49]

In an art therapy session, an adolescent is asked to use these materials to develop art around an idea. For example, teens might be asked to create:

- How do they think others see their portrait
- draw their sad feelings
- Collage of photos from magazine clippings about their feelings
- sculpt their family out of clay
- Make a mask to make them feel safer talking about their problems
- Visual diaries as another way to express feelings on a daily basis
- Participate in group art therapy

For some teens, traditional individual therapy can feel like grilling. Others cannot express themselves verbally well. In some cases, the teen's problems are too distressing or complex to express in words.

As an expressive therapy, art therapy can be very effective for some teens because it is:

- Not threatening, less directly focused on teens.
- A safe outlet to express their innermost feelings.
- The process by which adolescents feel a sense of control.
- Meetings are fun and creative.
- A method of uncovering underlying thoughts and feelings.
- It is easier to form a strong relationship with a therapist.

For some teens, art is a better language of communication than conversation. Because this is an attractive form of therapy for teens, they are more likely to remain engaged and persevere in the process until the problem improves. [50]

C. Application in entertainment life

In addition to the application of art therapy on some specific occasions, in fact, it can be implanted in more casual occasions, even in various details of life, to help everyone get more well-being and mental health. For example, some art forms of activities that already exist in our lives can include some art healing parts, such as providing some normal guidance so that everyone can have some different experiences in the process.

- **Movie.** Many people already have a habit of watching movies, that is, going to the cinema to watch movies, so in the process of watching movies, they can actually add some sense of experience to achieve a better effect of artistic healing. For example, movie theaters can design and upgrade some service experiences. The simplest, for example, you can place some promotional posters or manuals at the entrance of the movie viewing about how to heal yourself in the process of watching movies. By reading the content above, consumers can also master some methods of art healing to improve their viewing experience. This is a win-win approach for both customers and cinemas. Advertisements of non-profit organizations can also be embedded in the pre-screening advertisements of movies to help everyone build some understanding of mental health or art healing.
- **KTV.** Similarly, everyone also has the habit of going to KTV to sing. Music is also a very good way of artistic healing. In the link of KTV service design, it can also be upgraded to provide our customers with a better play experience, and at the same time, it can also produce some artistic healing effects. For example, in the pre-opening advertisement of KTV, or on some readily available cards in KTV, add some tips on how to achieve artistic healing effects through music, listening to songs, and singing, so as to increase the experience of our customers and achieve a win-win situation Effect.
- **Municipal construction.** Throughout the municipal construction, each of our cities will have many decorative flowers, trees, or some roadside promotional slogans. Some advertisements on the roadside can also moderately add some pictures of works of art with artistic healing effects or some text poems to help everyone have a better mood and improve their mental health. Through art therapy, The way of healing can improve the overall advanced level and overall humanistic accomplishment of a city.

- Shopping center. The same is true in shopping malls because when people visit shopping malls, they want to get a relatively pleasant physical and mental experience. , or to buy some delicious food or some very delicious afternoon tea time; in fact, all of these is a process of experience. Since it is an experience, art healing elements can be added to it so that everyone can achieve a better effect of decompression and enhance their sense of well-being. You can add some artworks that are conducive to art healing in the shopping mall, or some cards and short sentences of art healing to help everyone improve the feeling of art healing and enhance the experience of physical and mental relaxation in the shopping mall, to achieve a win-win situation.
- Airplane. When taking a plane, whether it is a long-distance plane or a short-distance plane, some films will be played on the plane, sometimes it is some funny short films, sometimes it is some movies, and sometimes it is some advertisements. Then, in order to improve the good feeling of customers during the entire flight experience and even bring some additional gains and benefits to customers, the materials played on the plane can actually be targeted to select some psychologically beneficial More effective videos or music can be played, so that you can better improve your customer satisfaction and achieve a win-win effect.
- Architectural design. In the process of architectural design, whether it is a residence or a school, you can consider how to design some buildings from the perspective of art healing or carry out some modeling design and some interior soft decoration design, such as Some hanging pictures, or some colors, to achieve the effect of artistic healing. By entering this environment every day in this way, it can subtly improve a person's mood, improve a person's mental sub-health state, help people to resolve some anxiety and pressure, and make people feel better in the process of silent tasks.
- Public transit. There are generally some advertisements painted on the bus, and these advertisements are sometimes advertisements for advertisement bidding or advertisements purchased by some enterprises. Then we can increase the display of some paintings related to art healing in a certain proportion of the bus, or the display of some beautiful language, or some large color blocks, to improve people walking on the road, or It is the effect of psychological healing for people who take public transportation. In this way, we can also use a very subtle way to improve the mental health of the whole people, reduce the crime rate, and make society better and better. It can also be used at bus stops.
- Student attire. In the clothing design of students, some art healing methods can also be applied, and some healing and stress-relieving colors or patterns can be integrated into the clothing design so that students can change their minds during the learning process. Become more peaceful and confident so that the pressure can be greatly buffered.
- Office design or factory design. In office design or factory design, many art healing methods can also be applied to design some soft interior decorations and some moving line diagrams so that people can have a better mood in the entire working scene. Because it is inevitable to face some pressure at work, or face some difficult moments, then how to let your employees achieve a better state of mind through art-healing design so as to generate better personal happiness and Work performance, which is also a very interesting application area.
- Nursing home. In nursing homes, how to enable the elderly to better find meaning in old age of life also requires some artistic healing methods to improve. We can better integrate art therapy into elderly service centers such as nursing homes or universities for the elderly so that the elderly can use some large blocks of time or fragmented time in art therapy to sublimate their life. Meaning, or to untie some of my previous knots so that my old age life has more colorful meaning. It can even be said that a group of elderly artists with very strong personalities has been cultivated to increase the breadth of personal experience in one life. Many aging problems can be solved through art therapy so that the elderly can experience extraordinary meanings in this period of life, even richer meanings than when they were young.

CHAPTER FIVE

CURRENT DIFFICULTIES AND CHALLENGES

A. Market Demand

Since art and psychological healing are relatively unfamiliar fields and topics for many people, many people do not have a usage habit or consumption habit in this regard. Therefore, in terms of market demand, the potential demand is actually huge, but the manifest demand is very little. Because many people still think that the perception of art is relatively out of reach, and the perception of psychological healing may still stay at the level that they think has nothing to do with themselves. Or rather. When the psychological problem is not particularly serious, they are unwilling to prevent or intervene in advance. People hope to improve their happiness and make their lives happier every day, but more often through other means, such as buying some items or traveling. Relatively speaking, people do not have a particularly high level of consciousness, and they use direct methods related to psychology to improve their own happiness and enhance their inner joy. So, on the whole, the market demand in this area is huge as Maslow's demand moves up, but this demand has not been discovered by consumers, and it is still a potential state.

B. The Ability of Art Therapy Coaches

The ability of an art therapy coach is actually a relatively high standard of ability. The reason is that this person must not only have a part of artistic accomplishment but also have very professional psychological knowledge, so the portrait of this person may be an Artist or an amateur art lover. At the same time, the person must have some background in psychology. For example, the person may have previously studied undergraduate, graduate, doctoral, or postdoctoral majors related to psychology, such as clinical psychology, developmental psychology, or cognitive psychology. Psychology, etc., then this talent can reach the qualification standard of an art therapy coach from a certain direction of his major and with the help of a relatively good art path. Art therapy coaches, together with some personal talents and acquired efforts, gradually bring more and more effective healing results to their customers in practice, bring more self-exploration to customers, and Help customers get out of their fundamental comfort zone, enjoy their life more happily, accept the test given in life more calmly, live out what they want more and more, improve happiness, and improve the whole person from the inside out performance, and even radiate to the person's performance in a series of abilities, work performance and career performance, as well as family performance, academic performance, and other aspects.

To sum up, the requirements for art therapy coaches are very high, so there must be a phenomenon, just like psychological counselors or just like practitioners in any industry, its quality is relatively low. Said it must be uneven. So when choosing this career, you need to consider your own strengths and weaknesses. Similarly, when customers choose an art therapy coach, they must also consider many factors comprehensively to make a choice that suits them.

C. Willingness to pay

In terms of willingness to pay, because the market of art therapy is relatively new, although there are already many people in the world who are already engaged in art therapy, the industry is still relatively small. New. Moreover, the users of art therapy are also relatively limited, so the overall willingness to pay in this regard will be relatively low. For example, the willingness to pay may be benchmarked in some regular painting classes or some regular clay sculpture studios. Wait, or some people will benchmark it against conventional psychological counseling. However, if it is a very capable art therapy coach, his charging standard should be higher or even much higher than the two industries just benchmarked. Therefore, in terms of willingness to pay, consumers pay. There are still some differences in the charging standards of art therapy coaches with high willingness and positioning. This also needs to be continuously tested by the market and improved by people's self-awareness.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

With the development of life, social development, and the improvement of everyone's requirements and self-realization, people will pay more and more attention to some psychological problems, and more people will hope to improve their happiness and enhance their psychological sub- A healthy state, and art therapy is a very good way. While meeting the expectations just mentioned, you can also improve the diversification of a person's lifestyle, enhance a person's taste and personal charm, and even master a new ability to become an artist. Art therapy is a very applied psychological healing method, and it is also a very distinctive and influential art practice method. It has been used on a global scale, and there will be more applications in the future that can effectively help everyone improve their mental health and behavioral performance.

REFERENCES

- [1.] "Art: Definition." Oxford Dictionary. Archived from the original on September 1, 2016. Retrieved 25 December 2015.
- [2.] Giovanni Schiuma (19 May 2011). *The value of art to business*. Cambridge University Press. Page. 37. ISBN 978-1-139-49665-0. Archived from the original on 5 August 2019. Retrieved 26 May 2018.
- [3.] Giovanni Schiuma (19 May 2011). *The value of art to business*. Cambridge University Press. Page. 37. ISBN 978-1-139-49665-0. Accessed from the original document on 5 August 2019. Retrieved May 26, 2018.
- [4.] Information Resource Management Association (2014, June 30). *Digital Arts and Entertainment: Concepts, Methods, Tools, and Applications*. United States: IGI Global. Page. 976. ISBN 978-1-4666-6115-8. Retrieved from the original document on 5 August 2019. Retrieved May 26, 2018.
- [5.] Trotter, Jeremiah (15 February 2011). "RiverKings uses art to raise autism awareness." WMC TV. From the original file on February 22, 2011.
- [6.] "Art Bras Bring Awareness of Reward." From the original file on October 19, 2019. January 1, nd25.
- [7.] "Want to increase visibility at ArtPrize." WWMT, News Channel 3. 10 January 2012. Archived from the original on October 6, 2012.
- [8.] Susan Hogan (2001). *Therapeutic Art: A History of Art Therapy*. Jessica Kingsley Press. ISBN 978-1-85302-799-4. Archived from the original on 5 August 2019. Retrieved 26 May 2018.
- [9.] "What is Psychotherapy?". www.psychiatry.org. Retrieved March 12, 2022.
- [10.] Malchiodi, Cathy A. (27 November 2013). *Expressive Therapy*. Guildford Press. ISBN 978-1-4625-1490-8.
- [11.] From A+ Medical Encyclopedia "Sub-health" entry <http://www.a-hospital.com/w/%E4%BA%9A%E5%81%A5%E5%BA%B7>
- [12.] Hogan, Susan (2001). *Therapeutic Art: A History of Art Therapy*. UK: Jessica Kingsley Publishers London and Philadelphia. Pages 21, 22. ISBN 1-85302-799-5.
- [13.] "On Art Therapy". British Association of Art Therapists. Retrieved 3 January 2018.
- [14.] Starkey, HL; Nobel, J (February 2010). "The Links Between Art, Therapy, and Public Health: A Contemporary Literary Review". *American Journal of Public Health*. 100(2): 254–63. doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2008.156497. PMC 2804629. PMID 20019311.
- [15.] Kaimal G, Ray K, Muniz J. Reduction in cortisol levels and participants' responses following art creation. *art therapy*. 2016;33(2):74-80. doi: 10.1080/07421656.2016.1166832
- [16.] Van Lith T. Art therapy in mental health: A systematic review of methods and practice. *Art in Psychotherapy*. 2016;47:9-22. doi:10.1016/j.aip.2015.09.003
- [17.] Italia, S., Favara-Scacco, C., Di Cataldo, A. and Russo, G. (2008). Assessment and art therapy for burnout syndrome in oncology departments. *Psycho-Oncology* 17, 676–680. doi: 10.1002/pon.1293
- [18.] Visnola D., Sprudža D., Ārija Bake M., Pike A. (2010). Effects of art therapy on employee stress and anxiety. *process. Latvian Academy. science. sect. B Nutt. exact application. science*. 64, 85-91.10.2478/v10046-010-0020-y
- [19.] Visnola D., Sprudža D., Ārija Bake M., Pike A. (2010). Effects of art therapy on employee stress and anxiety. *process. Latvian Academy. science. sect. B Nutt. exact application. science*. 64, 85-91.10.2478/v10046-010-0020-y
- [20.] Italia S., Favara-Scacco C., Di Cataldo A., Russo G. (2008). Assessment and art therapy for burnout syndrome in oncology departments. *Psycho-Oncology* 17, 676-680. 10.1002/pon.1293
- [21.] Crawford MJ, Killaspy H., Barnes TR, Barrett B., Byford S., Clayton K., et al. (2012). Group art therapy as adjunctive therapy in patients with schizophrenia: a randomized controlled trial (MATISSE). *health technology. Evaluate*. 16, 1-76. 10.3310/hta16080
- [22.] Leurent B., Killaspy H., Osborn DP, Crawford MJ, Hoadley A., Waller D. et al. (2014). Moderators of the effectiveness of group art therapy for schizophrenia: a secondary analysis of data from the MATISSE randomized controlled trial. *socialist party. Psychiatry Psychiatry. epidemiology*. 49, 1703-1710.10.1007/s00127-014-0876-2

- [23.] Richardson P., Jones K., Evans C., Stevens P., Rowe A. (2007). An exploratory randomized controlled trial of art therapy as adjunctive treatment for schizophrenia. *J. Spirit. Health* 16, 483–491. 10.1080/09638230701483111
- [24.] Crawford MJ, Killaspy H., Barnes TR, Barrett B., Byford S., Clayton K., et al. (2012). Group art therapy as adjunctive therapy in patients with schizophrenia: a randomized controlled trial (MATISSE). *health technology. Evaluate.* 16, 1-76. 10.3310/hta16080
- [25.] Leurent B., Killaspy H., Osborn DP, Crawford MJ, Hoadley A., Waller D. et al. (2014). Moderators of the effectiveness of group art therapy for schizophrenia: a secondary analysis of data from the MATISSE randomized controlled trial. *socialist party. Psychiatry Psychiatry. epidemiology.* 49, 1703-1710.10.1007/s00127-014-0876-2
- [26.] Chandraiah S., Anand AS, Avent LC (2012). Efficacy of group art therapy on depressive symptoms in adult heterogeneous psychiatric outpatients. *Art there.* 29, 80-86. 10.1080/07421656.2012.683739
- [27.] Thyme KE, Sundin EC, Stahlberg G., Lindstrom B., Eklof H., Wiberg B. (2007). Comparative results of short-term psychodynamic art therapy and short-term psychodynamic speech therapy in depressed women. *Psychoanalysis. Psychologist.* 21, 250-264. 10.1080/02668730701535610
- [28.] Kopytin A., Lebedev A. (2013). Humor, self-attitudes, emotion, and cognition in group art therapy for veterans. *Art there.* 30, 20-29. 10.1080/07421656.2013.757758
- [29.] Girija Kaimal, Kendra Ray, and Juan Muniz (2016) Reduction of cortisol levels and participants' responses after art creation, *Art Therapy*, 33:2, 74-80, DOI: 10.1080/07421656.2016.1166832
- [30.] Gussak, D. (2004). Art therapy for prison inmates: a pilot study. *Art psychiatrist.* 31, 245–259. doi: 10.1016/j.aip.2004.06.001
- [31.] Gussak, D. (2006). Effects of art therapy on prison inmates: a follow-up study. *Art psychologist.* 33, 188–198. doi: 10.1016/j.aip.2005.11.003
- [32.] Gussak, D. (2009b). Comparing the effectiveness of art therapy for depression and locus of control in male and female prisoners. *Art psychologist.* 36, 202–207. doi: 10.1016/j.aip.2009.02.004
- [33.] Sela N., Baruch N., Assali A., Vaturi M., Battler A., Ben GT (2011). Effect of medical art therapy on quality of life and medical compliance in patients with advanced heart failure. *Harley Law* 150, 79–83.
- [34.] Sudres JL, Anzules C., Sanguignol F., Pataky Z., Brandibas G., Golay A. (2013). Therapeutic education of patients with art therapy: Effectiveness in obese patients. *educate. Therapeutic Du Patient Therapeutic Patient Education.* 5, 213-218. 10.1051/tpe/2013032
- [35.] Feldman MB, Betts DJ, Blausey D. (2014). Process and Outcome Evaluation of an Art Therapy Program for People with HIV/AIDS. *Art there.* 31, 102-109. 10.1080/07421656.2014.935593
- [36.] Monti DA, Peterson C., Kunkel EJS, Hauck WW, Pequignot E., Rhodes L., et al. (2006). A randomized controlled trial of mindful art therapy (MBAT) in women with cancer. *Psycho-Oncology* 15, 363–373. 10.1002/pon.988
- [37.] Monti DA, Kash KM, Kunkel EJ, Brainard G., Wintering N., Moss AS, et al.. (2012). Changes in cerebral blood flow and anxiety associated with an 8-week mindfulness program in women with breast cancer. *Stress Health* 28, 397–407. 10.1002/me.2470
- [38.] Oster I., Svensk AC, Magnusson E., Thyme KE, Sjödin M., Åström S., Lindh J. (2006). Art therapy improves coping resources: a randomized controlled study in women with breast cancer. *Palliat. Support. Nursing* 4, 57-64. 10.1017/S147895150606007X
- [39.] Öster I., Magnusson E., Thyme KE, Lindh J., Åström S. (2007). Art therapy in women with breast cancer: therapeutic effects of boundary enhancement. *Art psychologist.* 34, pp. 277-288. 10.1016/j.aip.2007.04.003
- [40.] Bar-Sela G., Atid L., Danos S., Gabay N., Epelbaum R. (2007). Art therapy improves depression and affects fatigue levels in cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy. *Psycho-Oncology* 16, 980–984. 10.1002/pon.1175
- [41.] Svensk AC, Öster I., Thyme KE, Magnusson E., Sjödin M., Eisemann M., et al.. (2009). Art therapy improves the quality of life in women undergoing breast cancer treatment: a randomized controlled study. *EUR. J. Cancer Nursing* 18, 69–77. 10.1111/j.1365-2354.2008.00952.x

- [42.] Thyme KE, Sundin EC, Wiberg B., Öster I., Åström S., Lindh J. (2009). Personal brief art therapy may be helpful for women with breast cancer: a randomized controlled clinical study. *Palliat. Support. Nursing* 7, 87-95. 10.1017/S147895150900011X
- [43.] Monti DA, Peterson C., Kunkel EJS, Hauck WW, Pequignot E., Rhodes L. et al. (2006). A randomized controlled trial of mindful art therapy (MBAT) in women with cancer. *Psycho-Oncology* 15, 363–373. 10.1002/pon.988
- [44.] Monti DA, Kash KM, Kunkel EJ, Brainard G., Wintering N., Moss AS, et al.. (2012). Changes in cerebral blood flow and anxiety associated with an 8-week mindfulness program in women with breast cancer. *Stress Health* 28, 397–407. 10.1002/me.2470
- [45.] World Health Organization (2018). Child and adolescent mental health. Available online: https://www.who.int/mental_health/maternal-child/child_adolescent/en/ (accessed 11 August 2020)
- [46.] Riley S. *Contemporary Art Therapy for Adolescents*. London: Jessica Kingsley; 1999.
- [47.] Van Lith, T. (2016). Art therapy in mental health: A systematic review of methods and practice. *Art psychologist*. 47, 9-22. DOI: 10.1016/j.aip.2015.09.003
- [48.] *Front. Psychol.*, 08 October 2020 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.584685>
- [49.] Kathryn Rudlin, LCSW, California-based author and therapist who specializes in counseling and educating adolescents whose mothers are emotionally disconnected, 2020